

Reforms and Updates in Culture and Art Education – Guarantee of Quality Education

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Abstract: This article contains thoughts and opinions about the rapid reforms and prospective tasks in the improvement of the quality of higher education in New Uzbekistan. In particular, the activities of higher education institutions in the field of culture and art were analyzed. In this field, attention is paid to newly established higher education institutions and fundamental changes in education are discussed.

Keywords: culture and art, higher education, knowledge, skills, competence, quality of education, analysis.

The attention paid to education by the President of our country is so strong that on December 20, 2022, in his address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the people, he named the new year 2023 as “Year of attention to the people and quality education”. The petition says “Improving the quality of education is the only right way for the development of New Uzbekistan”. Indeed, the reforms carried out by President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev are gradually raising education to a higher level. Law No. 576 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2019 “On Science and Scientific Activity”, Decree No. 6097 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2020 “On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030” is important for the development of education and science in our country.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” was adopted on September 23, 2020, and its purpose is to regulate relations in the field of education.

The president gave a wise opinion about creating conditions for pedagogues and valuing them, – first of all, we will focus on supporting education, which is the biggest investment for New Uzbekistan. Salvation is in education, salvation is in upbringing, salvation is in knowledge. Because all good goals are achieved thanks to education and upbringing. These words of our ancestors should be turned into practical actions of our deputies and senators, political parties, local councils, the entire state apparatus, and the general public. Therefore, improving the quality of education in schools and the prestige of the teaching profession in society, improving the conditions of teachers will be one of our main tasks in 2023. I believe that the status of teachers, the protection of their honor and dignity should be defined separately in the Constitution – the head of our state emphasized[1:15].

In order to provide the industry with highly educated and qualified personnel, the following educational institutions were established. In particular, the National Pop Art Institute named after Botir Zakirov; Yunus Rajabi Institute of National Music Institute; Urganch branch of the State

Academy of Choreography of Uzbekistan; Nukus branch of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. Also, in the 2021/2022 academic year, a boarding school specializing in opera in the city of Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan, Primary dance boarding schools have been launched in the cities of Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Namangan and Urganch. Our youth is given great opportunities to showcase their talents. In particular, more than 400 young people participated in international and republic-level contests and festivals (traditional and online) and won prestigious places[2:2].

Today, the educational activities of higher educational institutions are further improved, and the quality of our people's desire for knowledge, formed over the centuries, is being demonstrated once again. Our young people should live a healthy and beautiful life, get a permanent job in their profession, take responsibility, not belittle their human dignity, in a word, achieve perfection. is striving and considers education as the most important activity in this process. The educational activity of universities is further improved, and the quality of our people's desire for knowledge, which has been formed over the centuries, is being demonstrated once again. Our young people should live a healthy and beautiful life, get a permanent job in their profession, take responsibility, not belittle their human dignity, in a word, achieve perfection. is striving and considers education as the most important necessity in this process. Learning is the basis of the development of human society. With science, man has shaped the society and the various political institutions within the society, so that all these serve for the development of mankind. The doctrine of "learn from the cradle to the grave" is also applied in the rules of humanity[3:17].

Today, the new Uzbekistan is gaining its place in the world community. Every sector in the country is being developed in a timely and appropriate manner, and every sector is breathing a breath of renewal. Let's not go far and stop only about reforms in the field of education. The reason is that in recent years special attention is being paid to the creation of a competitive environment in the system of school, secondary special and higher education in our country, the wide use of public-private partnership and private sector resources, and the inclusion of the population with higher education to the level of developed countries. On the basis of the public-private partnership system, the activities of non-governmental higher education institutions have been launched, great work is being done to acquire modern knowledge and skills of young people at the level of world standards, and to reveal their abilities and talents. Speaking about this, it is worth noting that new higher educational institutions and branches of the world's leading universities have been established, and the number of higher education institutions has reached 177. The society's needs for the scope and quality of higher education services are observed to increase sharply at the present time, which is reflected in the knowledge economy.

As a result of the acceleration of scientific and technical development, information and communication technologies, microprocessor technologies occupy a central place in the structure of production resources in the economy[4:8].

As a result of the implementation of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021, ensuring innovative and technological development in economic sectors and the social sphere, including agriculture, energy, construction, education, health care and great progress has been made in terms of promotion. In 2018, there were 6,500 young scientists, and in 2022, their number was 10,800, that is, it increased by one and a half times[5:2].

The education system is being consistently developed in order to educate young people to be knowledgeable and competent, to train experts in line with world development. The initial reforms in the field of higher education focused primarily on increasing coverage, improving the financial condition of institutes and universities, and providing financial support to professors and teachers. In particular, in the last 3 years, the number of higher education institutions has increased from 65 to 117, the number of admissions has increased from 66,000 to 181,000. Their material and technical base has been strengthened. Within the framework of joint education

programs with foreign countries, training of specialists in 64 new professions was launched. The salaries of professors and teachers were increased by an average of 3.5 times. For example, 55% of today's 815 directions do not meet the requirements of the labor market. Higher education institutions are not provided with textbooks on about 2,000 subjects, and educational programs are based on the subjects and directions of 40 years ago. In addition, there are many cases of corruption in the system. In general, 65 percent of the population said that the results of reforms in higher education are not noticeable. Therefore, the head of our state indicated 4 priority tasks in the field: the first is to increase the role of management boards of higher education institutions and expand the powers of departments. The second is to adapt the educational process to market requirements, ensure its integration with production, and create an environment for the student to work on himself.

The third is to increase the scientific potential of higher education institutions, to develop science and innovation. The fourth is to reduce red tape for faculty and students, and drastically reduce bureaucracy and corruption by digitizing the industry. In order to effectively fulfill these tasks, it was emphasized that higher education institutions should be empowered to make independent decisions on academic and organizational management[6:1].

Following the reforms in higher education in recent years, the reforms being carried out in higher education have said In recent years our universities have increased 2.5 times in the number of enterprises, 198 The extent was emphasized that the extent increased from 9% to 38%, and in this regard, the tasks did not depend on the issues related to the strengthening of education. In fact, many thousands of professors and teachers working in the field of higher education are not only witnesses of reforms in higher education, but also direct participants. As part of the reforms implemented in the higher education system in our country, special attention was paid to the issue of financial and academic independence of higher education institutions. To date, 41 higher education institutions in our country have received this status. We can say that the granting of financial independence to educational institutions created conditions for further expansion of the institution's capabilities in the higher education system. First of all, it serves to strengthen the material and technical base. Secondly, it creates an opportunity to apply advanced foreign experiences in the educational process of the institution, in particular, to involve professors and teachers of prestigious higher education institutions directly in the educational process. In addition, due to the attention to science, young scientists, the conditions created for their scientific and research work, the increasing scientific potential in the higher education system is also manifested as a result of the ongoing changes[7:4]. President Sh. Mirziyoyev: "Our people should know this very well: we have a long and difficult road ahead of us. If we all stick together, study tirelessly, do our work perfectly and effectively, acquire modern knowledge, and strive forward without sparing ourselves, our lives and society will definitely change" he calls on us to change our society.

For example, we should all work together to implement the tasks set forth in the appeal for the development of New Uzbekistan.

Today, when science and technology are developing at a rapid pace, the amount of scientific knowledge, understanding and imagination is increasing dramatically. This, on the one hand, ensures its differentiation due to the development of new fields of science and technology, and on the other hand, the process of integration between sciences is created. In such conditions, the demand for qualified pedagogues increases, it is necessary to train creative pedagogues who have mastered the fundamental foundations of science, pedagogy and psychology methods, have high professional training and can apply modern innovative pedagogical and information technologies in practice. Currently, the use of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development. This, in turn, requires paying special attention to the systematic introduction of innovations into the field of education, due to the rapid development of the modernization process in the country. However, the level of implementation of pedagogical scientific research on the introduction of new content, form, methods and tools of

teaching in this field cannot be considered sufficient at the moment[8:524]. Addendum of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on “Ensuring the openness of the activities of state bodies and organizations, as well as effective implementation of public control” on measures” in accordance with Decree No. PF-6247 dated June 16, 2021, of state higher education institutions financed from the republican budget within the system of the Ministry of Culture “On the implementation of annual income and expenses for 2022”[9:1].

INFORMATION

The name of the university	2022 annual performance				
	Total income	Total costs	of which, wages and equivalent expenses	other expenses	of which, construction costs
State Conservatory of Uzbekistan	16 400 231	63 598 391	56 320 171	7 278 221	
Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture	40 397 103	61 677 096	54 550 279	7 126 817	
Uzbek State Academy of Choreography	4 101 466	15 097 545	12 935 386	2 162 159	
Fergana regional branch of the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture	6 042 803	14 541 447	11 594 194	2 947 253	1 556 776
Nukus branch of the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture	8 664 210	17 347 259	15 730 244	1 617 015	
Uzbek National Institute of Musical Arts named after Yunus Rajabi	5 065 448	18 432 013	17 142 454	1 289 559	
Nukus branch of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan	333 307	4 169 972	3 779 789	390 183	
Urgench branch of the Uzbek State Academy of Choreography	559 192	2 526 150	2 421 100	105 050	
Institute of National Variety Art named after Batyr Zakirov at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan	1 788 447	4 739 678	4 601 469	138 210	
TOTAL	83 352 207	202 129 552	179 075 085	23 054 466	1 556 776

At the same time, the President’s decision on February 2, 2022 “On additional measures to further develop the sphere of culture and art” opened a new promising period in the development of our national music. By this decision, starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, students in general secondary education institutions will be taught the skill of playing at least one of the national musical instruments, and this result will be recorded in their certificate. 10,130 schools, 323 children’s music schools, 826 cultural centers are provided with 3 sets of 7 types of national musical instruments. 205 billion soums were allocated by our state for this purpose. Starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, educational institutions are working to improve the musical knowledge and skills of pupils and students, and to create love for our national music art in their hearts.

In particular, based on the needs of our youth, processing at least 150 of the best national songs for karaoke performance and educational institutions (during breaks), airports, railway and bus

stations, shopping and entertainment complexes, cultural and recreational parks, boulevards, hotels and special attention was paid to the preparation and popularization of music albums containing national tunes that will be broadcast through the local networks of other organizations and have a positive effect on the psyche of visitors (with respect to copyright).

As the great politician Nelson Mandela said, “Education is the most powerful weapon that can be used to change the world”. In this sense, the future of our country depends on the strategic correct organization of our educational system and the development of young people into knowledgeable and capable personnel. Today, the changes being made in the field of education in our country make people happy. Reforms were implemented in the system in order to expand the scope of higher education. In my opinion, the biggest task before us should be to increase the quality of higher education in parallel with the number of young people. For this, it is necessary to attract more strong expert lecturers and practical lesson teachers to our universities. In my opinion, if young people studying and working abroad are involved in the process of teaching at universities in their fields, the process of implementing international standards in educational institutions will accelerate and this will serve efficiency[10:62].

In recent years, the large-scale reforms implemented in our country regarding the fundamental improvement of the higher education system have placed a number of tasks before the higher education institutions. These include adapting the activities of higher education institutions to world standards, international accreditation of educational programs, entering the list of higher education institutions in the first 1000 of the ranking of internationally recognized organizations, developing external academic mobility, and others. Passing international accreditation helps to strengthen the position of higher education institutions in the republic at the international level, to actively enter the global process[11:8].

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